

IMI2 Project No 777372 - RESOLUTE

Research empowerment on solute carriers

WP8 – Knowledge integration and data management

D8.1 Data Management Plan 1

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² Public, fully open.

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Introduction

RESOLUTE is a public-private partnership with 13 partners from academia and industry with an overarching goal: To trigger an escalation in the appreciation and intensity of research on solute carriers (SLCs) worldwide and to establish SLCs as a tractable target class for medical research and development. Through the coupling of an inclusive, “open-access ethos” to the data, results, techniques and reagents with the highest-possible quality of research output, RESOLUTE expects to accelerate the pace and increase the impact of research in the field of SLCs to the global benefit of basic academic research through to applied research in SMEs and pharmaceutical companies.

Data management plays a major role in the project by providing a central data repository for collecting, curating, sharing, integrating, analysing and publishing data generated across the individual work packages and consortium members. This data management plan (DMP) describes the infrastructure, policies and life cycle for research data generated and/or processed throughout the RESOLUTE project. It is intended to be a living document and will be updated throughout the project whenever significant changes occur. The official and public data management plan is updated at mid-term (Deliverable 8.2) and a final data management plan is presented at the end of the project (Deliverable 8.3).

Research Data

Virtually every individual task of the RESOLUTE project depends on or produces data in order to develop reagents, deorphanize SLCs or set up assays. On the one hand, existing data in the public domain or with permissive licenses is collected and compiled into the RESOLUTE knowledgebase (Deliverable 8.4). A majority of data, on the other hand, is newly generated, processed and analysed throughout the project. This process is supported by the RESOLUTE database (Deliverable 8.5). Both resources are accessible from the RESOLUTE web portal at <https://re-solute.eu> (Deliverable 8.6; see Figure 1). For more details, please refer to *Data Curation: the RESOLUTE Data- and Knowledgebase* on page 12.

Figure 1. RESOLUTE web portal.

Ultimately, data generated in course of RESOLUTE will be disseminated through the RESOLUTE knowledgebase, among other means (see also *Data Lifecycle* on page 13).

Data Types

A multitude of types of data is expected to be produced in the course of the RESOLUTE project, ranging from primary data over scientific publications to reagents, analysis tools and workflows. The following table describes the different data types and levels, and their corresponding format, standards and relations in detail. Please note that this list will be significantly extended during the course of the project.

RNA-Seq measurements of cell lines

<i>Data Description</i>	RNA-Seq measurements of various cell lines using NGS
<i>Data Type</i>	Transcription profiling
<i>Data Level</i>	primary (raw)
<i>Data Format</i>	FASTQ (community accepted, open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	Illumina high-throughput sequencing of isolated RNA
<i>Meta Data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RNA isolation protocol - Library preparation protocol - Instrument type - Instrument method - Sample size - Sample description (source, treatment, timepoint, etc.)
<i>Quality Control</i>	Standardized quality control using FastQC software to assess: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Per base sequence quality (Phred scores) - Per base sequence content - Per sequence GC content - Per base N content - Sequence duplication level - Adapter content - K-mer content
<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 1.5 (parental cell lines, knockout and overexpression cell lines, required controls) Task 7.1 (knockout cell lines of priority SLCs under perturbation conditions)
<i>Data Author</i>	Boehringer (T1.5), Sanofi (T7.1)
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Serves as input to mapping to a reference genome (see <i>Alignments of RNA-Seq to reference genome</i> below).
<i>Data Volume</i>	10 TB (expected)
<i>Data Sustainability</i>	Data can be duplicated to following public repositories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EBI's sequence read archive (SRA) - Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO)

Alignments of RNA-Seq to reference genome

<i>Data Description</i>	Mapping of RNA-Seq to a reference genome
<i>Data Type</i>	Transcription profiling
<i>Data Level</i>	derived (processed)

<i>Data Format</i>	BAM: Binary Alignment Map (community accepted, open, binary format)
<i>Data Source</i>	Processing of raw reads from <i>RNA-Seq measurements of cell lines</i> on page 5
<i>Meta Data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Read trimming and clipping method - Used reference gene and transcript model (e.g. ENSEMBL GRCh38, release 94) - Software version and parameters used for read mapping
<i>Quality Control</i>	Custom analysis scripts to assess: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gene body coverage (no 3' bias) - Mapping rate - Unique mapping rate - Gene model mapping rate - Replicate correlation
<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 1.5 (parental cell lines, knockout and overexpression cell lines, required controls) Task 7.1 (knockout cell lines of priority SLCs under perturbation conditions)
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Serves as input to quantitative gene expression analysis (see <i>Quantitative gene expression of cell lines</i> below).
<i>Data Volume</i>	10 TB (expected)
<i>Data Sustainability</i>	Because of straightforward reproducibility, data from this intermediate step in transcription profiling will not be submitted to external repositories.

■ **Quantitative gene expression of cell lines**

<i>Data Description</i>	Quantitative gene expression analysis of various cell lines
<i>Data Type</i>	Transcription profiling
<i>Data Level</i>	interpreted (analysed)
<i>Data Format</i>	CSV comma-separated values (community accepted, open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	Analysis of gene-model mapped reads from <i>Alignments of RNA-Seq to reference genome</i> on page 5.
<i>Meta Data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data normalization procedure - Software version and parameters used for quantification - Statistical model used
<i>Quality Control</i>	Custom analysis scripts to assess: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clustering on PCA analysis of replicates - Reproducibility of previously published transcription profiles (if available)
<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 1.5 (parental cell lines, knockout and overexpression cell lines, required controls) Task 7.1 (knockout cell lines of priority SLCs under perturbation conditions)
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supports decision process on cell line selection for assay development in Work Package 3 - Input to priority list generation in Task 4.2 - Input to integrative analysis in Task 7.3

	- Data from Task 1.5 will be published in the RESOLUTE knowledgebase
<i>Data Volume</i>	0.5 TB (expected)
<i>Data Sustainability</i>	Data can be duplicated to following public repositories: - EBI's sequence read archive (SRA)

▪ **SLC-wide viability screen**

<i>Data Description</i>	Pooled viability screen using a SLC-wide sgRNA library
<i>Data Type</i>	pooled sgRNA profiling
<i>Data Level</i>	primary (raw)
<i>Data Format</i>	BAM (community accepted, open, binary format)
<i>Data Source</i>	Illumina high-throughput sequencing
<i>Meta Data</i>	- Library preparation protocol - Instrument type - Instrument method - Sample size
<i>Quality Control</i>	Standardized quality control using in-house scripts to assess: - Per base sequence quality (Phred scores)
<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 2.5 (Genetic interactions)
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Serves as input to mapping reads to the sgRNA library (see <i>Quantitative viability in SLC-wide screen</i> below).
<i>Data Volume</i>	2 TB (expected)
<i>Data Sustainability</i>	Data can be duplicated to following public repositories: - EBI's sequence read archive (SRA) - Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO)

▪ **Quantitative viability in SLC-wide screen**

<i>Data Description</i>	Viability of SLC genes as count tables of mapped sgRNAs
<i>Data Type</i>	pooled sgRNA profiling
<i>Data Level</i>	derived (processed)
<i>Data Format</i>	CSV comma-separated values (community accepted, open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	Demultiplexing and mapping of reads from <i>SLC-wide viability screen</i> above to a reference library.
<i>Meta Data</i>	- mapping parameters - sgRNA library used - barcodes used
<i>Quality Control</i>	Standardized quality control using in-house scripts to assess: - Mapping rate of barcodes - Mapping rate of guides
<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 2.5 (Genetic interactions)

<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Serves as input to genetic interaction analysis (see <i>Genetic interaction analysis</i> below).
<i>Data Volume</i>	0.1 TB (expected)
<i>Data Sustainability</i>	Because of straightforward reproducibility, data from this intermediate step in sgRNA profiling will not be submitted to external repositories.

▪ Genetic interaction analysis

<i>Data Description</i>	Statistical model and network for genetic SLC-SLC interactions based on pooled viability screens in knock out cell lines.
<i>Data Type</i>	pooled sgRNA profiling
<i>Data Level</i>	interpreted (analysed)
<i>Data Format</i>	CSV comma-separated values (community accepted, open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	Analysis of viability tables from <i>Quantitative viability in SLC-wide screen</i> on page 7.
<i>Meta Data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data normalization procedure - Statistical model used - Network representation thresholds
<i>Quality Control</i>	Custom analysis scripts to assess: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Count distributions and outlier detection - Clustering on PCA analysis of replicates and time points
<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 2.5 (Genetic interactions)
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supports decision process on cell line selection for assay development in Work Package 3 - Input to priority list generation in Task 4.2 - Input to integrative analysis in Task 7.3 - Data from Task 2.5 will be published in the RESOLUTE knowledgebase
<i>Data Volume</i>	0.1 TB (expected)
<i>Data Sustainability</i>	

▪ Interaction proteomics based on mass spectrometry

<i>Data Description</i>	Mass spectra of interacting proteins
<i>Data Type</i>	SLC-focused protein-protein interactions
<i>Data Level</i>	primary (raw)
<i>Data Format</i>	mzML (community accepted, open, XML-based format)
<i>Data Source</i>	LC-MS/MS (Thermo Orbitrap Mass Spectrometer)
<i>Meta Data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sample preparation protocol - Instrument type - Instrument method - Sample size

<i>Quality Control</i>	Standardized quality control using ProteomeDiscoverer / Skyline to assess: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Total ion chromatogram - Visual inspection of the “ion map”
<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 2.6 (AP-MS) Task 7.2 (BioID, AP-MS)
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Serves as input to peptide identification and quantification (see <i>Protein-protein interaction data</i> below).
<i>Data Volume</i>	5 TB (expected)
<i>Data Sustainability</i>	Data can be duplicated to following public repositories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ProteomeXchange

■ **Protein-protein interaction data**

<i>Data Description</i>	Peptides and proteins identified and quantified
<i>Data Type</i>	SLC-focused protein-protein interactions
<i>Data Level</i>	derived (processed)
<i>Data Format</i>	mzID (community accepted, open, XML-based format)
<i>Data Source</i>	Searching MS/MS spectra (from <i>Interaction proteomics based on mass spectrometry</i> on page 8) in a reference database and quantifying signal intensity.
<i>Meta Data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - reference protein database - search parameters
<i>Quality Control</i>	Standardized quality control using in-house scripts to assess: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - amount of contamination - success rate of peptide-spectrum-matching - score distributions in a target-decoy approach
<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 2.6 (AP-MS) Task 7.2 (BioID, AP-MS)
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Serves as input to interaction network analysis (see <i>Protein interaction network</i> below).
<i>Data Volume</i>	1 TB (expected)
<i>Data Sustainability</i>	Data can be duplicated to following public repositories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ProteomeXchange - PRIDE

■ **Protein interaction network**

<i>Data Description</i>	Statistical model and network for SLC focused protein-protein interactions.
<i>Data Type</i>	SLC-focused protein-protein interactions
<i>Data Level</i>	interpreted (analysed)

<i>Data Format</i>	CSV comma-separated values (community accepted, open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	Integrative analysis of identification and quantification data from <i>Protein-protein interaction data</i> on page 9.
<i>Meta Data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data normalization procedure - Negative controls used - Statistical model used - Network representation thresholds
<i>Quality Control</i>	Custom analysis scripts to assess: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intensity distributions and sample outlier detection - Clustering on PCA analysis of replicates - Integration of subcellular localization data - Integration of CRAPome reference data sets
<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 2.6 (AP-MS) Task 7.2 (BioID, AP-MS)
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Input to priority list generation in Task 4.2 - Input to integrative analysis in Task 7.3 - Data will be published in the RESOLUTE knowledgebase
<i>Data Volume</i>	0.1 TB (expected)
<i>Data Sustainability</i>	Deposition of high-confidence interaction data at: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - BioGRID - STRING - IntAct

■ **Quantitative ionomics**

<i>Data Description</i>	Quantitative determination of different isotopes
<i>Data Type</i>	Ionic profiling
<i>Data Level</i>	primary (raw)
<i>Data Format</i>	CSV comma-separated values (community accepted, open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	ICP-MS analysis of cell lysates
<i>Meta Data</i>	sample name, date of analysis, processing method, tune parameters
<i>Quality Control</i>	calibration curves, CV of replicates
<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 2.8 (Determination of SLCs using ions as (co-)substrates)
<i>Data Author</i>	Vifor (International) Ltd.
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	characterization of SLCs on ion activity input to priority list generation in Task 4.3
<i>Data Volume</i>	5 GB (expected)
<i>Data Sustainability</i>	potential data duplication to public repositories (<i>to be discussed</i>)

■ **Cell-based or cell-free assays using fluorescence readout**

<i>Data Description</i>	Quantitative SLC transporter assays, such as calcein quenching assay, fluorescent SLC or ligand binding or internalization assays, fluorescence polarization assay
<i>Data Type</i>	Spectrophotometric data, high content imaging (HCI)
<i>Data Level</i>	primary (raw) / derived (processed) / interpreted (analysed)
<i>Data Format</i>	Excel, Columbus, TIFF, GraphPad Prism, Microsoft PowerPoint and Word
<i>Data Source</i>	
<i>Meta Data</i>	sample name, date of acquisition, filter set, settings, pixel data
<i>Quality Control</i>	Performance of assay confirmed by appropriate controls and reference substrate / inhibitors; checked by a second person before release
<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 3.5 (Assays involving fluorescence); Task 6.1 (Assay development)
<i>Data Author</i>	Vifor (International) Ltd.
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Establishing assays to support WP3 and WP6
<i>Data Volume</i>	0.5 TB (if HCI assays performed)
<i>Data Sustainability</i>	These data are not compatible to public repositories. Could be part of scientific manuscripts or reports.

 ■ **Functional assays**

<i>Data Description</i>	Generation of robust cell-based and cell-free assays for SLCs
<i>Data Type</i>	Functional readout systems
<i>Data Level</i>	interpreted (analysed)
<i>Data Format</i>	Depending on the technology used: Kinetics or end-point values; substrates/activators dose/response curves
<i>Data Source</i>	Primary data by the new developed assays on parental cell lines, knockout and overexpression cell lines, purified expressed proteins, with their negative controls. Data from public sources (i.e. publications, databases, patents etc.).
<i>Meta Data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data normalization procedure - Software version and parameters used for quantification - Statistical model used
<i>Quality Control</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data robustness (i.e. RZ' factor) and reproducibility inter-experiments and over time - Reproducibility of eventual previously published data
<i>Data Origin</i>	Work package 6 (Generation of robust cell-based (high-throughput) and/or cell-free assay systems for all proteins on the SLC priority list)
<i>Data Author</i>	all participants of work package 6
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Input from WP1: stable cell lines and/or constructs' generation - Input from WP2: SLCs potential substrates for orphan SLCs - Input from WP3: most suitable technology to be used to set a functional assay - Input from WP4: priority target list to work on - Input from WP5: available expressed SLC proteins, for cell-free assay set up

<i>Data Volume</i>	0.5 TB (expected)
<i>Data Sustainability</i>	Data can be duplicated to following public repositories, upon consortium agreement: - IUPHAR or NIH databases

▪ SLC homology models

<i>Data Description</i>	Homology modeling
<i>Data Type</i>	3D models
<i>Data Level</i>	derived (processed)
<i>Data Format</i>	atomic coordinates in PDB format (community accepted, open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	public repositories (PDB, HGNC)
<i>Meta Data</i>	- Alignment files - Unrefined homology models
<i>Quality Control</i>	- Accuracy of the template/target alignment - Structure evaluation programs - Enrichment calculations to assess the models' utility for virtual screening
<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 8.5 (Data mining)
<i>Data Author</i>	UniVie
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	- Helps understanding the mechanism of transport - Useful to conduct SAR studies - Helps to predicts new compounds
<i>Data Volume</i>	2 TB (expected)
<i>Data Sustainability</i>	

This data management plan is a living document and this section on Data Types will be updated and extended regularly. Further data types to be defined comprise e.g. targeted and untargeted metabolomics data, small molecule binding, functional bioactivity data, high-content screening data, scripts, algorithms and software tools for data analysis and visualization, QSAR equations, computational models, and data mining workflows.

Data Ownership

Data is inherently owned by the institution of its producer (see also *Consortium Agreement* paragraph 7.1.1).

Data Curation: the RESOLUTE Data- and Knowledgebase

While data physically resides on the CeMM storage server (see *Secure Storage* on page 17), the RESOLUTE data- and knowledgebase represent the central points of data and knowledge management, data curation and data access throughout the RESOLUTE project.

The RESOLUTE database (Deliverable 8.5) provides an interface to *primary*, *derived* and *interpreted* data as well as corresponding *metadata*. Moreover, it is not limited to data, but is also used to identify and manage material (e.g. reagents, biological samples, etc.) and events (e.g. experiments, measurements, shipping, etc.). Thus, it enables linking data to its origin and allows efficient implementation of data lineage and data provenance

tracking. The RESOLUTE database has a restricted area, accessible to the participants only, and a public area, which is openly accessible.

The RESOLUTE knowledgebase (Deliverable 8.4) comprises mainly *reference* data, i.e. data compiled from external databases and resources. It is a comprehensive and accurate resource of integrated state-of-the-art knowledge on the various SLC families. Over the course of the project, it will be expanded by selected *interpreted* data sets, i.e. analysis results from data produced in RESOLUTE. The RESOLUTE knowledgebase is largely openly accessible and contains some extra views accessible to the participants only.

In summary, the RESOLUTE database is experiment and data set centric, while the RESOLUTE knowledgebase focuses on biological entities. Both tools will link to each other wherever appropriate.

Data Lifecycle

The generation of data takes place at the sites of participants and initially is stored locally. After passing a local quality control and an appraisal of relevance, data will be uploaded to the RESOLUTE database. This submission process requires annotation of metadata. Data in the RESOLUTE database is automatically available to all participants (see *Data Sharing* on page 14). To be publicly accessible, data has to go through a data dissemination procedure (see *Data Dissemination* on page 14). Selected interpreted data will be also published in the RESOLUTE knowledgebase.

Figure 2. Schema of data lifecycle including the data dissemination procedure in RESOLUTE.

Data Identifiers

We developed a RESOLUTE identifier schema following recently published recommendations for the field of life sciences³. The identifiers have to be short and robust, as they will not only be used for data but also for reagents and therefore have to be written/read to/from test tubes regularly.

³ McMurry JA, et al. Identifiers for the 21st century: How to design, provision, and reuse persistent identifiers to maximize utility and impact of life science data. PLoS Biol. 2017 Jun 29;15(6):e2001414. doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.2001414.

A RESOLUTE identifier starts with two letters, specifying the type of entity (e.g. CE for cell line). The main part consists of four alphanumeric characters specifying the actual entity. In the end, an optional checksum character adds redundancy and allows spotting typos. The main part encodes an incremental number, using the digits 0-9 and the letters A-Z with the exception of D, I, J, L, O, Q, U and Y because of their similarity to other digits or letters. This results in an alphabet of 28 symbols and thus a total of up to 614,656 words using four characters. The checksum character is taken from an extended alphabet (including Q, U and Y) and is calculated as modulo 31 (i.e. the next prime number). The identifier is not case sensitive.

This RESOLUTE identifier schema applies to all entries of the RESOLUTE database, and is therefore not limited to data, but also used to identify and manage material (e.g. reagents, biological samples, etc.) and events (e.g. experiments, shipping, etc.).

Data Sharing

All data generated or compiled is openly shared among all participants (see *Consortium Agreement* paragraph 8.1.2). Data is shared either via the RESOLUTE SharePoint (for documents, reports, etc.) or via the RESOLUTE database (for primary, derived and interpreted data).

For sharing data with the scientific community, please refer to *Data Dissemination* below.

Data Quality and Annotation

As well-structured and high-quality data is essential to higher-level analyses and data reuse, we implement multiple layers of data documentation, annotation and quality control.

When uploading data to the RESOLUTE database, a submission form requires the author to provide annotation and metadata, including consistent linkage to existing data. Once in the database, data can be reviewed and curated by all participants. While standardized data annotation is required (see also *Making data findable* on page 15), an additionally implemented Wiki system encourages also informal data annotation by free text comments.

As we expect RESOLUTE reagents and data to lay the foundation of future SLC research, highest possible quality standards have to be met. We implement quality control on three levels: A first quality control step happens at the site of data generation, and specification of corresponding quality control metrics (see *Data Types* on page 5) is required when submitting to the RESOLUTE database. In a second step of quality control, a *data release proposal* with a focus on data annotation and quality control has to be prepared before the public release of a data set. In case of a scientific publication in a journal, the peer-review process forms the third layer of quality control and assessment of data annotation. To ensure a peer-review step also for data releases without scientific publication, we implement *data annotation and release workshops* (see *Data Dissemination* below).

Data Dissemination

All relevant data, i.e. data generated or collected by the RESOLUTE project that passed certain quality control and data appraisal procedures, should be rapidly published open access. Publication procedure follows one of three different routes (please also refer to the three columns in the central panel *RESOLUTE database* in Figure 2):

- **data release:** Any participant can propose data for public release by submitting a written *data release proposal* to the Work Package 8 team, specifying the following details:
 - an abstract on the data,
 - the motivation for publication,
 - the data identifiers,
 - the annotation status,

- the standards compliance,
- assessment of quality control,
- license to use for publication.

Work Package 8 team will collect these proposals for further discussion in *data annotation and release workshops*, taking place regularly at consortium meetings or possibly also as tele conferences in between. Participation at the workshop is voluntary, and all participants will receive the collected data release proposals two weeks before the workshop. At the workshop, the proposals will be discussed in detail with the aim of curating data, extending and refining annotation and strengthening quality control, but there will be no immediate decision taken on publication. Within a week after the workshop, Work Package 8 team together with the proposal's authors will send out a refined version of the data release proposal to the *publication and dissemination officers* of all consortium partners. In case there are no objections within a 30 days review period, the data will be published and openly accessible in the RESOLUTE database. Minor objections can be directly resolved with the objecting participant, while major objections require an adaptation of the proposal, effectively restarting the review period.

- **supporting a scientific publication:** Data might also be disseminated as integral part or supplemental material to a scientific, peer-reviewed publication. For this route, the same *data release proposal* as described above has to be submitted to Work Package 8 team, but a data annotation and release workshop is not required. All scientific publications will follow the *gold* or *hybrid* open access policy by submitting the manuscripts to open access journals or by paying for this option in the subscription-only journals. For more details on dissemination in the form of scientific publications, please refer to the *Dissemination and Exploitation Plan* (Deliverable 9.2).
- **end of project:** At the end of the project (i.e. July 2023) we intend to release and make openly accessible a vast majority of all data within the RESOLUTE database that was not published before.

FAIR Data

Participants of the RESOLUTE consortium acknowledge that living a culture of openness for this project will benefit the whole community of solute carrier research. By ensuring that all generated research data will be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), the RESOLUTE data- and knowledgebase will efficiently lead to discovery, integration and innovation. To support these efforts, we established contact to the IMI project FAIRplus, which is expected to start early 2019.

Making data findable

To make something findable, a synthesis of identifiability, locatability, actionability and discoverability is required. All data in the RESOLUTE database will be *identifiable* by their automatically assigned, unique and persistent identifier (see *Data Identifiers* on page 13). The data is *locatable and actionable* by a direct mapping of the identifier to an URI (e.g. <https://re-solute.eu/CL0001>) as well as a corresponding CURIE (compact URI, e.g. RES:CL0001), which will be registered at the resolving system of identifiers.org⁴. The RESOLUTE data- and knowledgebase allows published data to be *discoverable* in a manual way via the user-friendly web interface, and in an automated way by implementing the Bioschemas⁵ specification.

In addition, data is annotated with an abstract and keywords (enabling free text search), a set of generic metadata (i.e. the data author, a link to the experiment and sample, timestamps, etc.) and a set of specific metadata (see *Data Types* on page 5). By building on established metadata standards (e.g. Dublin Core⁶, ISA⁷, MIBBI⁸, etc.) and controlled vocabularies, we increase the findability and interoperability of the data.

⁴ Wimalaratne SM, et al. Uniform resolution of compact identifiers for biomedical data. *Sci Data*. 2018 May 8;5:180029. doi: 10.1038/sdata.2018.29.

⁵ <http://bioschemas.org>

⁶ Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (<http://dublincore.org>)

⁷ Investigation/Study/Assay framework (<http://isa-tools.org>)

⁸ Minimum Information for Biological and Biomedical Investigations (<https://fairsharing.org/collection/MIBBI>)

Furthermore, we also encourage participants to use Open Researcher and Contributor Identifiers (ORCID) for referencing their contribution to published datasets.

To further increase exposure and findability, we will register the RESOLUTE data- and knowledgebase at FAIRsharing⁹, a registry for research standards and databases, and re3data¹⁰, a registry for research data repositories.

Making data openly accessible

All data generated or collected by the RESOLUTE project is posed certain quality control and data appraisal procedures. Data of sufficient quality and relevance will be stored and shared in the RESOLUTE database and, ultimately, will be openly accessible. Refer to *Data Dissemination* on page 14 for the different routes and timelines of data publication.

Data is available at the RESOLUTE web portal (<https://re-solute.eu>; Deliverable 8.6), which forms the entry point to the RESOLUTE data- and knowledgebase. They provide open access to published scientific papers, reports and research data without the need for authentication or special software (apart from a standards-compliant modern web browser). In addition, corresponding metadata and licensing information is provided.

We will also provide advanced tools for optimal data exploitation, i.e. a web based query system featuring interactive graphs and reports, and APIs and workflow support (e.g. KNIME¹¹ nodes) for automated database access and data mining (Deliverable 8.7).

Making data interoperable

Coherent use of non-proprietary, standardized data and metadata formats, aiming at maximum compliance with open source software applications, ensures interoperability of RESOLUTE data. To enable inter-disciplinary interoperability, relevant existing resources are referenced and metadata standards established across research domains are used (see also *Making data findable* on page 15).

Increasing data re-use

We support data re-usability by a rapid data generation to publication timeline, based on our streamlined data release process (see *Data Dissemination* on page 14). Upon publication, data is openly accessible (see *Making data openly accessible* above) and re-usable for third parties by a permissive open access standard license, provided either by the Creative Commons¹² or by the Open Data Commons¹³ project. Data re-usability is also increased by employment of strict data quality assurance processes (see *Data Quality and Annotation* on page 14).

Algorithms or analysis software tools developed in the course of the project that might be needed to re-use data and re-produce results will be published alongside the data.

Data Security

While there is no highly sensitive data (like patient data) in the RESOLUTE project and all data will be ultimately open access, data security is still a necessary and important issue. The following paragraphs list actual implementation and infrastructure details ensuring secure data storage, access and transfer.

⁹ <https://fairsharing.org>

¹⁰ <https://www.re3data.org>

¹¹ The Konstanz Information Miner (<https://www.knime.com>)

¹² <https://creativecommons.org>

¹³ <https://opendatacommons.org>

Figure 3. Overview on RESOLUTE data- and knowledgebase infrastructure and technology stack.

Secure Storage

Documents like SOPs, protocols, reports, or meeting minutes, are collaboratively written and stored in a SharePoint environment via a cloud-hosted service (Microsoft Office 365).

Data (primary, derived and interpreted data) are stored at local IT infrastructure of CeMM, managed by the CeMM IT department. The IT infrastructure at CeMM is currently in the process of receiving a significant upgrade to its storage hardware, and is expected to be fully operational mid of 2019. The full scale of estimated required storage volume for RESOLUTE (see *Data Stewardship* on page 18) will then be available.

To minimize the risk of data loss, a local backup strategy as well as a cloud backup strategy is in place. The local backup runs incrementally and writes to magnetic tapes (IBM Backup system). The cloud backup is provided by a Microsoft Azure cloud service and fulfils the rules of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). To rule out data manipulation or corruption we employ MD5 checksums.

Access to the CeMM storage server is strictly restricted and available only from within the CeMM intranet. Therefore, special means of secure data access and secure data transfer have to be established to allow participants to submit or review internal data, and to allow public users to view and download published data.

Secure Access

Participants of the RESOLUTE consortium have access to all the documents and information in SharePoint via a personalized RESOLUTE account, managed by a Microsoft Azure Active Directory service. Implementing an OAuth2 workflow, the same RESOLUTE account is used to securely access data and information in the internal sections of the RESOLUTE database and the RESOLUTE knowledgebase (see *Data Curation: the RESOLUTE Data- and Knowledgebase* on page 12).

Authenticated as well as unauthenticated (i.e. public) access to data and information in the RESOLUTE web portal, the RESOLUTE knowledgebase, and the RESOLUTE database will be protected by implementation of transport layer security using the secure communication protocol (HTTPS).

Secure Transfer

Data is produced by individual participants locally, but managed and stored centrally at the CeMM storage server. Offering a smooth user experience in this process requires fast and secure data transfer. As the CeMM storage server is only accessible locally (see *Secure Storage* on page 17), remote access and transfer via the internet to the CeMM storage server has to be mediated by some means. We employ three strategies for secure transfer:

1. As initial solution, we used the SharePoint environment, which provides an easy-to-use interface for data down- and upload. However, transfer of large files or transfer of a bulk of files turned out to be cumbersome, and data at the SharePoint has to be moved manually from or to the CeMM storage server.
2. As temporary solution, we set up a SFTP server with one dedicated user account per participant, allowing for easy programmatic transfer of many and/or large files. Again, data at the SFTP server has to be moved manually from or to the CeMM storage server on demand.
3. Starting from mid of 2019, we will employ a dedicated data transfer server. Data will be transferred from the CeMM storage server to this data transfer server automatically upon demand, where it is then available for download via the RESOLUTE web portal, the RESOLUTE database or the RESOLUTE knowledgebase. The same setup will also be used for data upload / data submission.

Data Sustainability

Published data is not only available via the RESOLUTE data- and knowledgebase, but is also submitted to technology-specific or domain-specific, community-accepted repositories wherever possible (e.g. EBI's Sequence Read Archive for next-generation sequencing data, ProteomeXchange for interaction proteomics data, or ChEMBL for compound/transporter interaction data). For data-type specific sustainability implementations please refer to *Data Types* on page 5.

Data structure, data formats, metadata formats and also code base are built on standards defined by major public initiatives, such as the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) or HUPO Proteomics Standards Initiative, ensuring compatibility and sustainability.

Data Preservation

All data entering the RESOLUTE database will be stored for the course of the project. The RESOLUTE data- and knowledgebase will be supported by CeMM for at least 5 more years after the end of the project. After that, for long-term preservation, the diligent use of domain specific standards will ensure that all data will be transferable to corresponding certified public data repositories. A detailed data preservation plan will follow in the mid-term update on the data management plan (Deliverable 8.2).

Data Stewardship

CeMM is hosting the server infrastructure. We estimate production of a total data volume of 300 TB throughout the project, corresponding to a data production rate of 5 TB per month. Required resources for storage and backup are provided by CeMM (see *Secure Storage* on page 17) and are budgeted with a total of 200,000 EUR.

CeMM (in particular Ulrich Goldmann) is also responsible for data management, with strong support from UniVie (in particular Gerhard Ecker). At least one representative per participant takes part in the monthly tele conferences on RESOLUTE data management (Work Package 8).

Two individuals per participant are responsible for data dissemination as *publication officers*. In addition, all participants are encouraged to engage in the regular *data annotation and release workshops* (see *Data Dissemination* on page 14).

Ethical and Legal Considerations

There is no personal data generated in the RESOLUTE project. However, data is generated on human cell lines and for details please refer to the ethics report (Deliverables 10.1 and 10.2).

External data which might be collected and re-used (e.g. for the RESOLUTE knowledgebase) is scrutinized for ethical or legal compliance beforehand.

Appendix

Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
AP-MS	Affinity purification mass spectrometry
CURIE	Compact Uniform Resource Identifier
CV	Coefficient of Variation
DMP	Data Management Plan
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
HTTPS	Hyper Text Transfer Protocol Secure
ICP-MS	Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry
ID	Identifier
LC-MS/MS	Liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry
MD5	Message Digest algorithm; used for calculating file checksums
NGS	Next-Generation Sequencing
OAuth2	Open Authorization 2.0
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier
PCA	Principal component analysis
QSAR	Quantitative Structure–Activity Relationship
RESOLUTE	Research Empowerment on Solute Carriers
RNA-Seq	RNA (ribonucleic acid) sequencing
SAR	Structure–Activity Relationship
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
SLC	Solute Carrier
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

Consortium Members

short name	full name
CeMM	CeMM Research Center for Molecular Medicine of the Austrian Academy of Sciences
UoX	University of Oxford
UoL	University of Liverpool
AXXAM	Axxam SpA
ULei	Universiteit Leiden
MPIMR	Max-Planck Institut für medizinische Forschung
UniVie	Universität Wien
Pfizer	Pfizer Ltd.
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG
Boehringer	Boehringer Ingelheim
Vifor	Vifor International Ltd.
Sanofi	Sanofi Aventis Recherche et Développement
Bayer	Bayer AG